

THROUGH RAINBOW SPECS: WORKPLACE INCLUSIVITY EXPERIENCE AMONG LESBIAN, GAY, BISEXUAL, AND TRANSGENDER MEMBERS

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Through Rainbow Specs: Workplace Inclusivity Experience among Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender Members

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Abstract

This study examined workplace inclusivity experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and others (LGBT) using the Self-affirmation Theory, Workplace Belongingness, and Motivation. With Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, LGBT from diverse industries in Batangas were questioned utilizing a semi-structured interview. This study aimed to explore the inclusivity experience of LGBT members in their workplace and proposed comprehensive activities that can help promote an inclusive workplace effectively. To do this, the researcher examined the responses of the LGBT members. It was found that Self-affirmation Attributes; Conditional Positive Self-View; Self-affirmation Strategies for Self-esteem; Workplace Inclusivity, and Belonging; Diverse Spectrum of Workplace Facilities and Treatment for LGBT Groups; Sustainable Approaches to Inclusivity and Gender Equality Efforts; Dualistic Workplace Experiences; Innate Motivation Perform; Diverse External Motivators and Demotivators; and Fulfillment and Motivation in Assigned roles existed as part of their workplace experience. This study also recommended a Comprehensive Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Value Proposition to be adopted in the workplace.

Keywords: *LGBT, workplace inclusivity, self-affirmation, belongingness, motivation*

Introduction

“Cause shade never made anybody less gay.” — Taylor Swift

Despite the splashes of glitters, unicorns and rainbow shades, lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and other (LGBT) members have been experiencing more mental health challenges compared to the other heterosexual and cis-gender folks, usually driven by exclusion, stigma, and discriminations. Mental health outcomes from these groups have been poorer, particularly due to emotional distress, bullying, victimization, stereotyping, stigma discrimination, and roadblocks to accessing healthcare services.

Viewing this spectrum through rainbow specs or sharing experiences from their shoes could be a better way to address these pain points. This prism of a minority group has always been a topic for arguments in the diversity spectrum as to its acceptance in the Philippine setting. Diversity and inclusion talks have always been a hall of fame for their controversy in the global work industries along with black people, ethnic groups, religious communities, and people with special abilities.

While a lot of theories had existed, one cannot deny the fact that there are a lot more considerations, and “whys” are not a question to their SOGIE but more on “who” and “how” they identify themselves with. Providing a safe space for LGBT individuals has been the focus of most organizations in the Philippines. People in this spectrum are one of the hot seats in bullying, discrimination, exclusion, and assaults. These instances could create long-term and deep harm to these groups hence it is important to explore this study to help in any way by exploring their lived experiences and recommending programs that would help protect and create safe space for these individuals.

Workplace inclusion, one of the key themes in the Philippine SOGIE Bill, plays a vital role in creating an environment where each of the LGBT members can be authentic to themselves whatever the colors of their SOGIE are. In the past years, leaders of organizations including lawmakers have recognized that a society of discrimination and exclusivity could create serious harm and have been designing programs to address it.

These programs, while having strong clauses on paper, have been implemented inadequately with the absence of effective execution and monitoring. This creates low affirmation and assurance in the confidence and safety of the minority group. Hence, the researcher aims to explore the inclusivity experience of LGBT members and propose helpful activities that will help promote inclusive spaces in their workplace effectively.

Moreover, there was a growing pride movement and awareness in the Philippine settings. This also entailed good context in local employment, as the inclusivity of the minority group was already being celebrated. However, there were still challenges to cultural acceptance and the minority group still had a long way to go.

This research is relevant to today's time and poses great importance as it serves as a basis for the possible profile, as well as tendencies and characteristics, an LGBT individual may have according to the lived experiences they shared. This research may help organizational leaders and future researchers to better understand LGBT sector needs based on the emerging key themes from this study. This study may also serve to determine the career path, an individual in the minority group may mind productive, and also in the selection of job positions most fitted to certain specific profiles.

Having access to their experiences was like riding a sleigh on a rainbow—while colorful, it was also diverse. It was a mix of emotions

and a full combination of various enchanting and curiosity questions.

Research Questions

This research investigation aimed at identifying the workplace inclusivity experience among LGBT members. It answered one central question: What is the essence of lived experience of LGBT members regarding workplace inclusivity?

1. How do the LGBT describe their experiences on the aspect of workplace inclusivity?
2. What themes emerge from the testimonies of LGBT?
3. Based on the findings of the study, what compendium of inclusive activities or programs can help LGBT overcome the challenges on workplace inclusivity may be proposed?

Literature Review

Spectrum of LGBT and SOGIE

In the past, SOGIE stood as an abbreviation for sexual orientation, gender identity, and (gender) expression. It had always been associated with the LGBT community, as everyone had a sexual orientation and a gender identity. It alluded to traits that applied to all people. Everyone, including lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender individuals, expressed their gender.

According to Nazario (2022), sexual orientation can be divided into categories—heterosexual, bisexual, homosexual, pansexual, and asexual. Heterosexual individuals were attracted to people of one's opposite gender. Bisexuals were attracted to the same gender or different from themselves. Homosexuals were those who were attracted to one's own gender identity while pansexual ones were attracted to people of any. Lastly, asexual individuals were not sexually attracted to all other people.

LGBT in the Philippine context

Philippines, while known to be one of the friendliest countries for LGBT, was also in a quest acknowledging the community as part of its culture. As a Catholic-populated state, many of the LGBT members were still facing discrimination anywhere and the workplace was not an exemption. (De Guzman, 2022).

Workplace Diversity and Inclusivity

More each day, organizations were being mindful and strategic in the critical importance of workplace inclusion. Across commerce, businesses benefited from employees of diverse backgrounds with equal opportunities and resources to utilize in the workplace (Day, 2022).

While it was known that diverse organizations beat less diverse competitors in profits, revenues, and employee satisfaction, hiring applicants from various backgrounds to maintain diversity was not sustainable without a culture of inclusion that embraced individuals for their true colors and encouraged them to succeed at work. Even with internal workplace policies that protected LGBT employees, the organization's culture impeded employees from bringing their authentic selves to work (McKinsey & Company, 2020).

Mental Health of LGBT Individuals

In US Census bureau data during the coronavirus pandemic, File and Marlay (2022) cited that lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) adults consistently reported greater rates of anxiety and sadness than non-LGBT persons. LGBT adults aged 18 and above reported about twice as many mental health issues as non-LGBT adults. In their earlier studies, younger participants were more likely to identify as LGBT and older ones experience more hardships in coming out because of having to be criticized by existing and previous acquaintances.

Unlike cisgenders in the workplace, according to Anawhar (2021), LGBT members often face challenges like being excluded, isolated, or ignored when they failed to meet the expected outcomes in the workplace. Heterosexual employees, on the other hand, generally do not face these challenges and enjoy more privileges, opportunities, and protections at work. They can express their identity and relationships without fear of discrimination or retaliation. They can also benefit from the dominant culture and norms that favor heterosexuality and cisgender identity. They may not be aware of the difficulties and barriers that LGBT employees encounter, or they may hold biases or stereotypes that contribute to the problem.

It was seen in his study that LGBT employees often face discrimination, harassment, and stigma at work, which can negatively affect their well-being, performance, and career prospects

Methodology

Participants

The population of the study comprised twelve (12) full-time regular employees from different work industries who are part of the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender sector in the Province of Batangas, with three (3) per sexual orientation. Personal and documented consents were prioritized with the participants ranging from employment legal age, 18 up to their 40s.

Instrument

This research study aimed to provide answers to the central and corollary questions, using observations and interviews to conclude. The goal was to collect information from the participants of the study through a semi-structured interview.

Procedure

This study underwent various steps and procedures in gathering the data. After complying with the necessary requisites for them to be able to conduct their study, the organization that was the subject of their study was identified.

To obtain authorization to conduct a study among LGBT people, the consent forms were sent along with the questionnaires to the target participants of the study. Purposeful homogeneous and snowball sampling was used, a non-probability sampling method in which participants were recruited to be part of the sample by other participants.

The study's goals, anticipated methodology, and the semi-structured research questionnaires that were given to participants were all attached to the written request. After receiving the forms, the interview schedules were set up. Even though the COVID-19 safety rules were relaxed across the board, online platforms was still chosen to conduct the one-on-one interviews. A Zoom link with recording, and a semi-structured 60-minute interview questionnaire with the participant's permission was set up. The interview was transcribed verbatim following the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) once all the relevant material and information were gathered.

When approaching data analysis in IPA, distinct vantage points were found by the researcher and external auditor. Both expressed their lens or theoretical framework to make sure that each understood their point of view. As a result, the auditor was better able to understand and analyze the data in light of the goals and emphasized the ideas of the researcher until the themes were finalized.

Ethical Considerations

To protect participants' rights and well-being, it was crucial to respect ethical standards when conducting research and gathering opinions from the LGBT community. Informed consent was sought from the participants and they were given the option to choose whether to participate and were guaranteed the ability to opt out at any moment without suffering repercussions. The required precautions to handle and preserve data securely, utilizing anonymization methods as necessary were taken.

It was also crucial to be sensitive to the LGBT community's cultural and social environment. The variety within the community, including the intersections of gender, sexuality, ethnicity, and other identities, was carefully understood and acknowledged. In consideration of the possible effects of the study on the LGBT community reporting the findings was done in a way that participants' experiences and dignity were respected.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

The findings of the study are presented in Matrices generated from the thematic analysis.

Matrix 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>SOGIE</i>	<i>Work Industry</i>	<i>Age</i>
RLL	Lesbian	HR Services	29
MCL	Lesbian	Food Industry	28
JAL	Lesbian	Public Administration	37
KTG	Gay	Legal Services	39
RJG	Gay	Education	32
JBG	Gay	BPO	25
MBB	Bisexual	Education	38
ADB	Bisexual	Engineering Company	32
CBB	Bisexual	Food Industry	24
KMT	Transgender	Construction	28
MIT	Transgender	HR Services	27
EPT	Transgender	BPO	24

Matrix 1 shows the profile of LGBT members in the Province of Batangas. This includes SOGIE. Work Industry and Age which were relevant to the objectives of the study. For respondents from members in the lesbian community, ages ranged from 28 to 27 while for gay community, 25 to 39; followed by bisexual, 24 to 38 and lastly transgender at 24 to 28.

Matrix 2 displays the graphic presentation of the themes that emerged from the responses of the participants. On the phenomenological

study on the lived experiences of LGBT members ten (10) themes emerged. These were: Self-Affirmation Attributes; Conditional positive self-view; Self-Affirmation Strategies for Self-Esteem; Workplace Inclusivity and Belonging; Diverse Spectrum of Workplace Facilities and Treatment for LGBT Groups; Sustained Approaches to Inclusivity and Gender Equality Efforts; Dualistic Workplace Experiences; Innate motivation to perform; Diverse External Motivators and Demotivators; and Fulfillment and Motivation in Assigned Roles

Matrix 2. Themes, and Subordinate Themes

<i>Final Themes Of The Study</i>	
<i>Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>
Positive Self-Affirmation Attributes	None
Conditional positive self-view	None
Self-Affirmation Strategies for Positive Self-Esteem	Optimism
Workplace Inclusivity and Belonging	Discrimination Acceptance
Diverse Spectrum of Workplace Facilities and Treatment for LGBT Groups	Inclusive facilities and workspace
Sustained Approaches to Inclusivity and Gender Equality Efforts	Gender Expression Gender Equality and Inclusivity
Dualistic Workplace Experiences	Feelings of exclusion Acceptance
Innate motivation to perform	None
Diverse External Motivators and Demotivators	None
Fulfillment and Motivation in Assigned Roles	Purpose Self actualization

Under the first theme, the members of LGBT shared their ways of self-affirmation in a positive light. As seen from their responses, most of them featured positive attributes about themselves such as being capable, persistent, morally upright, trustworthy, and selfless. It shows that participants were aware of the positive things about them, and they affirm themselves knowing they exhibit these traits and characteristics.

For the second theme, the participants shared their experiences regarding their view of themselves as conditional or variable to their achievements or the comments of people around them. It was implied from the responses that their fear of disappointing people has contributed to the ways they viewed themselves. To them, achievements and validations were important matters that affirmed them about being true to themselves. This was as if such titles or recognitions would lower their sense of self-acceptance.

Under the third theme, the participants shared their self-affirmation strategies for sustaining self-esteem in the workplace. Strategies derived from their responses included optimism, distancing oneself from people, keeping oneself from oversharing, being true to oneself, and giving the best in the workplace all the time. As a subtheme and common denominator for this case, optimism had been identified. This relates to how they continued to see things in a positive light despite their individual experiences.

For the fourth theme, the participants discussed the reasons and scenarios of how their experience with coming out and being true to themselves in the workplace, therefore themes of discrimination and acceptance were generated as a result of this experience. Each had different experiences but then again, good or bad, experiences teach them ways to cope and affirm themselves.

With the fifth theme, the participants expressed their experience with the availability of gender-inclusive environments and facilities their workplaces offered. It was almost average to find organizations and industries that offered gender-neutral facilities and with those who do not have it, experiences of harassment and exclusions had been found. These real situations were crucial in defining the matters to be addressed for each aspect.

For the sixth theme, the participants talked about their workplace management's attempt to achieve inclusivity. Most of them declared about the availability of inclusivity efforts to achieve gender equality. This generated subthemes, gender expression, and gender equality and inclusivity. Both of these were essential in improving the ways workplace belongingness and inclusivity are experienced by LGBT members.

Under the seventh theme, the participants shared their experiences about feelings of difference and wellness threats in the workplace when their workmates knew them for their SOGIE. This generated subthemes of feelings of exclusion and acceptance, an either-or experience most LGBT members had. While some of them were out loud with peers, stories about hiding their gender preferences just to fit in are also common.

With the eighth theme, the participants spoke about the innate matters motivating them and their reasons for working. Various areas were discussed such as conscientiousness, passion for work, inspired by familial stories, self-expression, and social circles. While each of them had different innate motivators in working, it can be noted from these derived responses that LGBT employees in the workplace each had their reasons to perform.

The ninth theme covered the external matters discussed in the study such as salary, treatment from the environment, workmates, and material aspirations. These matters were discussed in a domino effect how these things affected their overall workplace experience.

From simply salary and benefits to feelings of security and confidence transitioning, conversations like these were important to understand what externally drives their behavior and experience in the workplace.

Finally, in the last theme, the participants discussed their experiences with self-actualizing and finding purpose within their workspaces. While many of them continue to bump into roadblocks in the workplace such as harassment, discrimination, and microaggression, most of them are aware of the purpose they see for themselves and the implication of self-actualizing. Understanding that these subthemes arise from a rough situation truly is an inspiring reality of the beautiful idiom, “rainbow after the rain.”

Conclusions

Delving into this study and managing conversations with LGBT members further understand their experiences, hardships, and voices. The months spent doing this research unfolded a tapestry of emotions. It was foreseen and was able to inspect indelible scars from stigma, cultural stagnancy, and microaggressions through rainbow specs in a proximal level to LGBT members.

Some of the members from these groups, like the rest of everyone, who were only trying to balance life by stepping into the workplace and trying to make their work and relationships inside meaningful have been forced into a wall of ignorance and oppression. Post this research, it is hoped that their journey to their confidence and transformation continues to live on.

As the researcher plummeted down on this reflection, she was most grateful for these groups for further opening her eyes and being part of this transformation. She hoped that the workplace would no longer be just a cubicle for productivity and income generation but also a sanctuary where being authentic and proud thrives.

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